

SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING EFFECT ON SMARTPHONE INDUSTRY TOWARDS PURCHASE INTENTION: THE MEDIATION OF BRAND TRUST, BRAND IMAGE, AND BRAND AWARENESS

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Abstract

This research aims to determine how much Samsung smartphone consumers' purchase intention is influenced by social media marketing, where brand trust, brand image and brand awareness are mediating variables. This research used a quantitative approach by distributing questionnaires to 212 respondents, which were distributed online via social media. Data processing in this study used SmartPLS 4.0.9.4 software using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). Based on the results of the data analysis that has been carried out, each hypothesis in this research has a significant positive influence. It was explained that in this research, social media marketing has a significant positive effect on purchase intention, brand trust, brand image and brand awareness. Likewise, brand trust, brand image and brand awareness have a significant positive effect on purchase intention. The third mediating variable used in this research had a significant positive influence on mediating the relationship between social media marketing and purchase intention. This study allows the Samsung Company to increase their consumers' purchase intention, especially by focusing on future sales of their smartphone products more accurately and also provides insight into managing their social media marketing.

Keywords: Social Media Marketing, Purchase Intention, Brand Trust, Brand Image, Brand Awareness, Smartphone Industry

INTRODUCTION

With the increasingly rapid development of technology, human life has become much easier. Even today, humans can only live their daily lives with the help of technology. In one house, there is at least more than one technology with various functions. It cannot be denied that technology does have a big influence on human life because technology can facilitate human needs every day (Magang, 2023). Humans are curious and have a highly practical nature, so humans continue to innovate to create things that can make their activities easier. One very significant technological development is the development of information and communication technology (Putri, 2022) The presence of information and communication technology can make it easier for humans to communicate long distances without being limited by space and time (Suartama, 2023). There is an innovation that combines various functions of communication tools into one tool, namely a smartphone. Smartphones are considered to have become a primary need for people in Indonesia because by using smartphones, people can do many things and greatly speed up all their current needs (Jumlah, 2021).

According to data analyzed by (Ahdiat, 2023), the percentage of smartphone ownership in Indonesia increases every year. The increase in the number of smartphone users in Indonesia has clearly created competition in the smartphone industry. Every smartphone company is competing to develop the latest, more modern and sophisticated features so that more and more users are interested in their products. Therefore, if companies can have a significant influence on the products they have, it will increase the possibility of consumers choosing the products they sell.

There is a comparison of market share data for smartphone brands in Indonesia for the period January – June and July – December 2022, where there was a decrease in market share of 0.44% for the Samsung smartphone brand. Samsung was previously in first position, then replaced by the Oppo smartphone brand (Statcounter, 2022). The comparison can be used as a benchmark for the Samsung Company in improving the performance and quality of existing or future products. Regarding this problem, there is one means or way to communicate the latest product innovations and features to consumers, namely by using social media (Ningsih, 2022). One platform that facilitates users to exchange information, communicate and interact is by using social media.

Social media is considered to help a company to market and promote its products effectively, as seen from current technological advances, where most people access social media every day (Wijayanto, 2023). The advantage of marketing and promotions on social media for companies is that it is easier to reach consumers, provide interesting information, and build consumer interest in the products offered. In this way, consumers will be interested in purchasing products and can increase the number of sales of products being marketed (Ningsih, 2022).

Indonesia has a total of 204.7 million internet users, with the number of active social media users in Indonesia being 191.4 million users. The social media platforms that are most widely used in Indonesia currently are Instagram and Facebook (TheGlobalStatistics, 2023). Samsung has attempted to carry out marketing and promotions through social media, including Instagram, Facebook, Twitter and TikTok. By using four social media platforms, Samsung has many followers. This research focuses on people who follow Samsung Indonesia's Facebook because it has the most followers, namely 162 million followers. That number of followers allows Samsung to reach its consumers easily.

To increase its market share in Indonesia, the Samsung company can make Facebook the focus in promoting its products by paying attention to several things (such as dimensions or indicators in social media marketing) that suit the minds or thoughts of its consumers (Vedhitya, 2023). Several studies examine social media marketing, including research conducted by Kim and Ko (2010), which reveals that there are five dimensions or factors contained in social media marketing, including entertainment, customization, interaction, trend, and word-of-mouth.

The results of research by Moslehpour *et al.* (2022) indicate that the five dimensions or factors of social media marketing can significantly increase consumer buying interest. This research also reveals that brand image and brand trust have a mediating role. Therefore, brand image and brand trust make consumers interested in buying more positively with the influence of

social media marketing. In addition, Sanny *et al.* (2020) surveyed with results showing that to increase consumer buying interest in the products offered, companies can increase their brand image and brand trust through the right social media platforms to reach their customers in terms of marketing strategies.

Research conducted by Dewi *et al.* (2022) obtained the results that there is a significant influence between social media marketing and brand awareness. This research states that brand awareness has a positive effect on purchase intention, where brand awareness helps consumers recognize and understand the product or brand, which will ultimately influence consumer interest in buying it. Brand awareness in this research also has a mediating role in the relationship between social media marketing and purchase intention, meaning that this can trigger consumers to decide to purchase the product after finding much information about the product or brand.

The study by Guha *et al.* (2021) shows that social media marketing activities have a very strong impact on creating brand awareness and brand image in the social media sphere. This research also measures the effect of brand awareness and brand image on purchasing interest with positive and significant results. Then, observations made by Yadav and Rahman (2017) validated that social media marketing significantly influences purchase intention. Therefore, social media marketing contributes to an efficient marketing communication technique. This research also emphasizes the importance of all dimensions or factors in social media marketing to create effective marketing.

Meanwhile, Hanaysha (2022), who conducted research based on the influence of social media marketing features on purchasing decisions with the mediation of brand trust between the two, succeeded in showing that social media platforms play an important role in helping companies to achieve the desired marketing goals because the main purpose of advertising and marketing promotions is to build brand trust and captivate consumer purchasing behaviour.

It is necessary to know what affects the decline in Samsung smartphone sales seen from its social media marketing by adding consumer views based on brand image, brand trust and brand awareness so that Samsung smartphone products can continue to survive in the Indonesian market and achieve company goals. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct research with updates based on previous research so that Samsung can know what strategies should be used to reach consumers so that consumers have an interest in buying its products.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Social Media Marketing

Social media marketing is an activity in conveying and communicating offers of goods or services to increase the company's popularity and profits in its target market (Solomon *et al.*, 2018). Social media marketing aims to provide benefits (something of value to consumers that is conveyed through communication) and to increase consumer awareness and knowledge about the products of a company or brand (Solomon *et al.*, 2018). In digital marketing, social media is the most influential part because it can support communication between customers

and companies regarding service or product information so that companies can analyze customer desires and provide feedback to improve consumer perceptions of the company Chaffey and Chadwick (2017). This research uses dimensions of Social Media Marketing, which refer to research by Kim and Ko (2010), where there are five dimensions in social media marketing: entertainment, customization, interaction, word-of-mouth promotion, and trends.

Entertainment is an important component to encourage consumers to express positive or negative feelings about a brand in memory (Bilgin, 2018). Customization on social media is a means for a company to communicate the special features of their brand and increase consumer loyalty to that brand (Seo and Park, 2018). Interaction is defined as the exchange of information and opinions between one consumer and another or between consumers and certain brands and companies (Godey et al., 2016). Word-of-mouth is also ideal because consumers can discuss and disseminate brand-related information to colleagues, family, friends, and others without obstacles (Godey et al., 2016). Trendiness is the presence of the latest news on topics that are still hotly discussed, which is why most consumers often turn to social media to get information (Godey et al., 2016).

Brand Trust

Brand trust is a consumer's sense of security and trust in a particular brand where the brand can satisfy their desires so that when consumers trust the brand, purchases will be created, leading to consumer commitment to the brand. Brand trust can generate consumer interest in a particular brand when consumer needs and desires are met (Sanny et al., 2020). Then, according to Hanaysha (2022), brand trust arises when consumers have confidence in the satisfaction of a product. When trust grows, it can make it easier for the company to convey marketing information, and consumers will instil a good impression of the brand. Brand trust has a high-value role in influencing the behaviour of a person or group of consumers, and brand trust can have a positive influence on interest and purchasing decisions.

Brand Image

Brand image is a subjective and objective phenomenon regarding consumers' views of certain brands that are believed in their minds. To create a brand image perception, consumers do not need experience with the product or service offered but can generate consumer perception from brand information they receive from various related sources (Guha *et al.*, 2021). Brand image is always considered an essential factor in marketing because it allows marketers to study consumer behaviour when consumers like a brand, where consumers tend to share positive information by word of mouth with other consumers to compare with their competitors (Guha *et al.*, 2021).

If the consumer's perception of the brand image is very high or firm, it can generate interest in buying the product. Brand Image can represent consumers' perceptions, views and attitudes about a particular brand (Sanny et al., 2020). Companies must pay attention to how to create high brand image value because when consumers have a high brand image perception, they will continue to follow product developments from the company and ignore competitors, making it very profitable (Moslehpour et al., 2022).

Brand Awareness

Brand awareness means recognizing and remembering a particular brand from consumers' minds in sufficient detail to encourage consumers to make purchases. Purchases will be more accessible when consumers recognize a brand quickly because brand awareness can provide the basis for brand equity (Kotler and Keller, 2016). Brand awareness is also related to consumers' attitudes towards remembering and recognizing a brand in various circumstances and purchasing decisions. Brand awareness is essential because it can gather consumer thoughts to influence purchasing decisions (Zahid and Dastane, 2016).

Furthermore, according to Martins *et al.* (2019), brand awareness is related to the influence of a particular brand that remains in the minds of consumers and can be realized from the consumer's ability to remember and recognize a specific brand in different circumstances or conditions. Brand awareness is considered necessary because creating brand awareness can trigger a consumer's decision to evaluate and buy a product. Brand awareness is fundamental because it can influence and become a reference for consumers interested in purchasing a product. A brand is also the part of a product that consumers will remember first.

Purchase Intention

Purchase intention is a behavioural statement of the possibility of consumer availability in purchasing a product from a particular brand. Consumers can measure purchase intention on a scale from very unlikely to very likely (Solomon *et al.*, 2018). According to Belch *et al.* (2020), purchasing interest is generally based on the match between purchasing motives and brand characteristics consumers consider. Creating buying interest involves many processes consumers feel, such as motivation, perception, attitude formation, and integration. Purchase interest and purchasing activities are very different. When consumers are interested in buying a product from a particular brand, the consumer still has to decide when to buy and calculate the costs that the consumer must be prepared to purchase.

Kotler *et al.* (2018) say that consumers can form purchasing interest based on the value of a product that consumers expect, the price, and the benefits of the product that consumers expect. Apart from that, buying interest can occur due to two other factors: unexpected situational factors and factors based on other people's attitudes. Unexpected situational events can change a consumer's buying interest, for example, when there is damage or failure to operate a particular product while the consumer watches a product demo. Meanwhile, other people's attitudes can shape buying interest when the words of someone considered necessary by the consumer influence the consumer's possibility of buying a product. Purchase interest arises because of the consumer's feelings or expectations about the price, benefits and value obtained when buying the product. Purchase interest can change due to two factors, namely unexpected situational factors and other people's attitude factors.

Hypothesis and Conceptual Framework

There is research on social media users in Indonesia, where social media marketing significantly influences brand trust (Moslehpour *et al.*, 2022; Puspaningrum, 2020). This is

supported by research by Sanny *et al.* (2020), which states that most consumers are easily influenced by advertising on social media and this has an impact on their brand trust. Therefore, marketing strategies via social media make it easier for customers to get brand-related information on social media to increase customer trust in the brand. Thus, the formulation of the hypothesis is as follows:

H1: Social media marketing has a significant positive effect on brand trust in Samsung smartphones.

Research conducted by Damayanti *et al.* (2021), Bilgin (2018), and Mileva and Fauzi (2018) found that social media marketing had a significant positive effect on brand image. In addition, related research says that social media marketing is a very effective marketing tool. When social media marketing for a product gets better, it will increase the brand image (Damayanti *et al.*, 2021; Bilgin, 2018; Mileva and Fauzi, 2018). The hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H2: Social media marketing has a significant positive effect on brand image in Samsung smartphones.

There is also research that says social media marketing has a significant positive influence on brand awareness because the results obtained reveal that social media is considered an ideal two-way interaction platform for increasing brand awareness through various information and interactions (Dewi *et al.*, 2022; Bilgin, 2018). These findings align with research by Guha *et al.* (2021), who assume that when social media users learn about a product from various platforms, they will develop a positive brand image for that product. The hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H3: Social media marketing has a significant positive effect on brand awareness in Samsung smartphones.

There is research that supports brand trust has a significant positive effect on purchase intention (Moslehpour *et al.*, 2022; Sanny *et al.*, 2020), then there is research that finds that brand image has a positive effect on purchase intention (Sanny *et al.*, 2020; Guha *et al.*, 2021), and there is research that states that high brand awareness is a condition that can motivate consumer's buying interest positively or in the sense that brand awareness has a significant positive effect on purchasing intentions (Dewi *et al.*, 2022; Guha *et al.*, 2021). Based on this, the hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

H4: Brand trust has a significant positive effect on purchase intentions for Samsung smartphones.

H5: Brand image has a significant positive effect on purchase intentions for Samsung smartphones.

H6: Brand awareness has a significant positive effect on purchase intention for Samsung smartphones.

The level of consumer buying interest will be more significant when a brand's social media marketing can be managed well. Research reveals that social media marketing has a positive significant effect on purchase intentions, where social media is very effective as a platform for companies to offer their products, including new products and others (Moslehpour *et al.*, 2022; Dewi *et al.*, 2022). There still needs to be research that uses brand trust, brand image, and brand awareness as mediation between social media marketing and purchase intention, especially using social media Facebook as the primary means of marketing Samsung smartphones. The hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

- H7:** Social media marketing has a significant positive effect on purchase intentions for Samsung smartphones.
- H8:** Brand trust, brand image, and brand awareness have a significant positive effect in mediating the relationship between social media marketing and purchase intention on Samsung smartphones.

Based on the results of previous research described above and the hypotheses that have been developed, the conceptual framework of this research is as follows:

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

METHODOLOGY

The method used in this research is a quantitative method by collecting primary data and secondary data. The primary data used in this research was collected from questionnaires distributed online using the Google Forms platform. The population used in this research were

smartphone users in Indonesia, with an age range of 15 years to 54 years. Questionnaire respondents who can be used as samples in this research are people who have used or are currently using Samsung smartphone products in Indonesia, with the criteria being people who follow Samsung Indonesia's Facebook and intend to buy a Samsung smartphone in the future.

Sample calculations in this study used the determination of the minimum sample size for SEM, according to Hair *et al.* (2019). This research requires a minimum sample of 210 respondents. Because this research uses stratification based on the age of the respondents, the number of respondents who can represent the age range from 15 years to 54 years is 212. There are 33 indicators in the questionnaire, which will be answered by respondents using a Likert scale measurement type with a scale range of 1, which means "strongly disagree", to a scale range of 5 which means "strongly agree".

Meanwhile, secondary data was obtained from previous scientific journals, ebooks, and articles, which can be used to support the topics raised in this research. The data processing system used in this research is SmartPLS software version 4.0.9.4. The data that has been obtained is then processed using Structural Equation Model (SEM) analysis with outer model, inner model, Goodness-of-Fit (GOF), and hypothesis testing. The variables used in this research are Social Media Marketing (X) as the independent variable, Purchase Intention (Y) as the dependent variable, Brand Trust (Z1), Brand Image (Z2), and Brand Awareness (Z3) as the intervening variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The obtained respondent data in this study showed that male respondents dominated, with 115 respondents or 54.2% of the total respondents. Then, the number of respondents with female gender was 97 respondents or 45.8% of the total respondents. If we look at the age range, there were 57 respondents (26.9%) with an age range of 15 to 24 years, 57 respondents (26.9%) with an age range of 25 to 34 years, 53 respondents (25%) with an age range of 35 to 44 years old, and 45 respondents (21.2%) with an age range of 45 to 54 years.

In this study, there are three screening questions, where the screening question aims to sort respondents so they can match the criteria required in this study. The screening questions in this study were "Do you currently use or have ever used a Samsung smartphone?", "Do you follow Samsung Indonesia's Facebook?", and "Do you have an intention in buying Samsung smartphone products in the future?". The 212 respondents answered "Yes" to the three screening questions, which means this research obtained 212 respondents following the predetermined criteria. Subsequently, data analysis was carried out based on the answers from 212 respondents.

Measurement Model (Outer Model)

In testing the outer model, two things will be analyzed, namely validity analysis, which includes convergent validity and discriminant validity, and reliability analysis, which contains Cronbach alpha and composite reliability. Based on the results of data processing via SmartPLS, an outer model image of this research was obtained, which can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: PLS Algorithm Outer Model

Convergent validity can be valid if the AVE value is > 0.50 and the loading factor value must be > 0.70 . The convergent validity results in this research can be seen in Table 1. The AVE value and loading factor value from this research data analysis show that each questionnaire item has good capabilities and is declared valid in explaining each construct.

Table 1: Convergent Validity

Variable	Item	AVE	Loading Factor	Status
Social Media Marketing	SMM1	0.538	0.736	Valid
	SMM10		0.708	Valid
	SMM11		0.710	Valid
	SMM14		0.726	Valid
	SMM15		0.738	Valid
	SMM16		0.729	Valid
	SMM2		0.738	Valid
	SMM4		0.743	Valid
	SMM5		0.733	Valid
	SMM8		0.775	Valid
SMM9	0.745	Valid		
Brand Trust	BT1	0.637	0.793	Valid
	BT2		0.830	Valid
	BT3		0.802	Valid
	BT4		0.804	Valid
	BT5		0.761	Valid
Brand Image	BI1	0.734	0.858	Valid
	BI2		0.826	Valid
	BI3		0.888	Valid
	BI4		0.855	Valid
Brand Awareness	BA1	0.722	0.835	Valid
	BA2		0.806	Valid
	BA3		0.862	Valid
	BA4		0.918	Valid
	BA5		0.823	Valid
Purchase Intention	PI1	0.656	0.868	Valid
	PI2		0.818	Valid
	PI3		0.839	Valid
	PI4		0.842	Valid
	PI5		0.805	Valid
	PI6		0.773	Valid
	PI7		0.719	Valid

Source: Processed data result (2023)

The criteria in the discriminant validity test in this research are by looking at the Fornell-Lacker Criterion value, the cross-loading factor value, and the heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) value, where the cross-loading value of each variable must be higher than the cross loading factor value of the variable. Others, while the heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) value must show a figure <0.90.

Table 2: Fornell-Lacker Criterion

Construct	BA	BI	BT	PI	SMM
Brand Awareness	0.850				
Brand Image	0.519	0.857			
Brand Trust	0.520	0.517	0.798		
Purchase Intention	0.715	0.670	0.627	0.810	
Social Media Marketing	0.558	0.415	0.702	0.608	0.735

Source: Processed data result (2023)

Table 3: Cross-Loading Factor

	Social Media Marketing	Brand Trust	Brand Image	Brand Awareness	Purchase Intention
SMM1	0.486	0.427	0.487	0.835	0.580
SMM10	0.453	0.392	0.458	0.806	0.573
SMM11	0.483	0.426	0.387	0.862	0.614
SMM14	0.491	0.481	0.442	0.918	0.673
SMM15	0.455	0.481	0.438	0.823	0.591
SMM16	0.365	0.490	0.858	0.488	0.570
SMM2	0.325	0.438	0.826	0.400	0.564
SMM4	0.371	0.413	0.888	0.401	0.593
SMM5	0.362	0.431	0.855	0.492	0.568
SMM8	0.575	0.793	0.409	0.424	0.477
SMM9	0.567	0.830	0.376	0.412	0.538
BT1	0.570	0.802	0.382	0.394	0.495
BT2	0.565	0.804	0.444	0.405	0.504
BT3	0.525	0.761	0.455	0.445	0.487
BT4	0.522	0.530	0.537	0.666	0.868
BT5	0.510	0.498	0.560	0.574	0.818
BI1	0.488	0.527	0.605	0.571	0.839
BI2	0.524	0.543	0.584	0.572	0.842
BI3	0.521	0.527	0.519	0.568	0.805
BI4	0.461	0.492	0.517	0.553	0.773
BA1	0.413	0.430	0.468	0.545	0.719
BA2	0.736	0.492	0.306	0.430	0.457
BA3	0.708	0.462	0.294	0.437	0.431
BA4	0.710	0.492	0.313	0.406	0.418
BA5	0.726	0.527	0.297	0.399	0.430
PI1	0.738	0.569	0.296	0.400	0.410
PI2	0.729	0.598	0.235	0.388	0.409
PI3	0.738	0.473	0.315	0.421	0.486
PI4	0.743	0.493	0.357	0.376	0.485
PI5	0.733	0.493	0.318	0.409	0.461
PI6	0.775	0.567	0.317	0.421	0.459
PI7	0.745	0.508	0.309	0.423	0.463

Source: Processed data result (2023)

Table 4: Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

	Brand Awareness	Brand Image	Brand Trust	Purchase Intention	Social Media Marketing
BA					
BI	0.521				
BT	0.521	0.519			
PI	0.712	0.668	0.625		
SMM	0.558	0.415	0.702	0.605	

Source: Processed data result (2023)

Table 5: Reliability

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Brand Awareness	0.928	0.930
Brand Image	0.917	0.918
Brand Trust	0.897	0.898
Purchase Intention	0.931	0.932
Social Media Marketing	0.928	0.928

Source: Processed data result (2023)

The Fornell-lacker criterion from this research can be seen in Table 2, which produces a higher value compared to the correlation value between other variables. Then, from Table 3, it can be seen that all questionnaire items in this study are declared valid because they have a cross-loading factor value that is greater than other constructs or variables. Furthermore, based on Table 4, it is known that all variables used in this study have a heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) value < 0.90 , which means that the variables in this study are categorized as discriminantly valid. The results of all variables used in this research (social media marketing, brand trust, brand image, brand awareness, and purchase intention) have a Cronbach's alpha value > 0.7 and a composite reliability value > 0.7 in Table 5. This can be interpreted as meaning that all the variables in this study are reliable.

Structural Model (Inner Model)

R-Square

Based on Table 6, it can be seen that the influence of the social media marketing variable on brand awareness is 0.311, which means the brand awareness variable has a weak model, namely 31.3%, then the influence of the social media marketing variable on brand image is 0.172, which means the brand variable image has a weak model, namely 17.2%, then the influence of social media marketing on brand trust is 0.493, which means the brand trust variable has a weak model, namely 49.3%, while the influence of brand trust, brand image and brand awareness variables on purchase intention is 0.680, which means the purchase intention variable has a moderate model, namely 68%.

Table 6: R-Square

	R-square	Result
Brand Awareness	0.311	Weak
Brand Image	0.172	Weak
Brand Trust	0.493	Weak
Purchase Intention	0.680	Moderate

Source: Processed data result (2023)

Effect Size (F-Square)

Table 7 presents the predictor level of the brand awareness variable on purchase intention, the brand image variable on purchase intention, and the social media marketing variable on brand image have a medium influence because the F-square value is >0.15 . Furthermore, the predictor level of the brand trust variable on purchase intention and the social media marketing variable on purchase intention has a minor influence because the F-square value is > 0.02 . Then, the predictor level of social media marketing variables on brand awareness and social media marketing on brand trust has a major influence because the F-square value is > 0.35 .

Table 7: F-Square

Variable	F ²	Result
Brand Awareness -> Purchase Intention	0.262	Medium
Brand Image -> Purchase Intention	0.222	Medium
Brand Trust -> Purchase Intention	0.032	Minor
Social Media Marketing -> Brand Awareness	0.451	Major
Social Media Marketing -> Brand Image	0.208	Medium
Social Media Marketing -> Brand Trust	0.973	Major
Social Media Marketing -> Purchase Intention	0.033	Minor

Source: Processed data result (2023)

Predictive Relevance (Q-Square)

Table 8 presents the results where the variables brand awareness, brand image, brand trust, and purchase intention have a predictive relevance value because they have a Q-square value > 0 . The results of the analysis show that the variables brand awareness and purchase intention have a moderate model, the brand image variable has a weak model, and the brand trust variable has a strong model.

Table 8: Q-Square

Variable	Q ²	Predictive Relevance	Result
Brand Awareness	0.261	Yes	Moderate
Brand Image	0.136	Yes	Weak
Brand Trust	0.405	Yes	Strong
Purchase Intention	0.310	Yes	Moderate

Source: Processed data result (2023)

Path Coefficient

Table 9 presents that the seven hypothesis paths have positive path coefficient values, which means that the direction of the relationship between the variables in this study has a significant positive influence.

Table 9: Path Coefficient

Hypothesis paths	Path Coefficients
Brand Awareness -> Purchase Intention	0.379
Brand Image -> Purchase Intention	0.331
Brand Trust -> Purchase Intention	0.151
Social Media Marketing -> Brand Awareness	0.558
Social Media Marketing -> Brand Image	0.415
Social Media Marketing -> Brand Trust	0.702
Social Media Marketing -> Purchase Intention	0.153

Source: Processed data result (2023)

Goodness of Fit (GoF)

Goodness of Fit (GoF) is calculated from the square root of the average community index (AVE) and average R-Square values. The average community index (AVE) value of this research is 0.6574, and the average R-square value is 0.414. Based on calculations, the Goodness of Fit (GoF) value obtained from this research is 0.521. Therefore, the Goodness of Fit (GoF) value of the research model is included in the large GoF value category so that it can be well applied to future research.

Hypothesis Testing

The direct effect hypothesis and indirect effect hypothesis in this research are included in the one-tailed hypothesis, so the conditions for accepting the hypothesis test in this research are if the t-value > t-table (1.65) and the p-value < 0.05 then H0 is rejected; then if the t-value < t-table (1.65) and p-value > 0.05 then H1 is rejected.

Table 10: Hypothesis Testing

Direct Effect	T statistics	P values
BA -> PI	4.631	0
BI -> PI	4.533	0
BT -> PI	1.937	0.026
SMM -> BA	8.635	0
SMM -> BI	5.45	0
SMM -> BT	12.448	0
SMM -> PI	1.945	0.026
Indirect Effect	T statistics	P values
SMM -> BT -> PI	1.887	0.030
SMM -> BI -> PI	3.584	0.000
SMM -> BA -> PI	3.809	0.000

Source: Processed data result (2023)

Based on the results of the hypothesis test in table 10 by looking at the t-value and p-value, it can be seen that:

1. The results of the direct effect hypothesis test showed that brand awareness has a significant positive influence on purchase intention because the t-statistic value obtained is 4.631, which is greater than 1.65, and the p-value obtained is 0, which is smaller than 0.05. These results prove that consumers' high brand awareness of a product can increase their purchase intention. These findings are also in line with previous research from Moslehpour *et al.* (2022). A high perspective of brand awareness can create benefits for the company because the company can efficiently market its products without introducing the brand first. Therefore, to create high brand awareness, companies can carry out marketing well and in a targeted manner so that the message they want to convey to consumers can be conveyed so that consumers can remember, and that would create high brand awareness.
2. The results of the direct effect hypothesis test showed that brand image has a significant positive effect on purchase intention because the t-statistic value obtained is 4.533, which is greater than 1.65, and the p-value obtained is 0, which is smaller than 0.05. In line with Bilgin (2018) research, the results of this research show that a highly positive consumer perspective towards a product can make the company very profitable. A high brand image can make consumers recommend a product to colleagues without realizing it; this can happen because consumers will consider the product to be very efficient and very suitable for use.
3. The results of the direct effect hypothesis test showed that brand trust has a significant positive effect on purchase intention because the t-statistic value obtained is 1.937, which is greater than 1.65, and the p-value obtained is 0.026, which is smaller than 0.05. Consumer trust is no less important than anything else. By making consumers trust the product, it is possible for consumers to not switch to another brand because the consumer's experience with the product is outstanding. These results are in accordance with previous research conducted by Guha *et al.* (2021).
4. The results of the direct effect hypothesis test showed that social media marketing has a significant positive effect on brand awareness because the t-statistic value obtained is 8.635, which is greater than 1.65, and the p-value obtained is 0, which is smaller than 0.05. These findings indicate that high or low brand awareness can be influenced by social media marketing. Therefore, the Samsung company can market via social media to achieve high brand awareness. Following Sanny *et al.* (2020) research, social media marketing has empirically shown that increasing brand awareness and brand awareness can also influence consumer decision-making. These results also indicate that when social media users learn about a product from various platforms, they will develop a positive impression of it.
5. The results of the direct effect hypothesis test showed that social media marketing has a significant positive effect on brand image because the t-statistic value obtained is 5.45, which is greater than 1.65, and the p-value obtained is 0, which is smaller than 0.05. This

means that companies must utilize social media marketing to create a high brand image. By understanding what must be considered when conducting marketing aimed to improve brand image, companies can easily have a good brand image. Following Damayanti *et al.* (2021) research results, the better a company's social media marketing, the more it will influence its brand image.

6. The results of the direct effect hypothesis test showed that social media marketing has a significant positive effect on brand trust because the t-statistic value obtained is 12.448, which is greater than 1.65, and the p-value obtained is 0, which is smaller than 0.05. Hasil ini didukung oleh penelitian Sanny *et al.* (2020). Sanny *et al.* (2020) research supports these results. These results also show that most consumers are easily influenced by social media marketing, and this has a significant impact on their trust. Apart from that, marketing strategies through social media make it easier for customers to get information related to brands on social media to increase customer trust in brands, and companies must always pay attention to the products they offer.
7. The results of the direct effect hypothesis test showed that social media marketing has a significant positive effect on purchase intention because the t-statistic value obtained is 1.945, which is greater than 1.65, and the p-value obtained is 0, which is smaller than 0.05. In contrast to previous research from Dewi *et al.* (2022), all dimensions of social media marketing in this research have a significant positive influence on purchase intention. By prioritizing social media marketing, companies will increase the attractiveness of the products being marketed, making it possible to create consumer interest in buying these products. Therefore, companies can package social media content in a unique, interesting way, following the latest trends and interactively so that it can generate high consumer buying interest.
8. The results of the indirect effect hypothesis test show that the variables brand trust, brand image, and brand awareness as mediating variables have a significant positive effect on purchase intention because the respective t-statistic values obtained are 1.887, 3.584, and 3.809, which are greater than 1.65, then the p-values obtained respectively are 0.030, 0, and 0 which are smaller than 0.05. These results prove that brand trust, brand image and brand awareness are essential in mediating between social media marketing and purchase intention. This means that companies must focus on combining brand trust, brand image and brand awareness as targets in their marketing. If the company's social media marketing can increase brand trust, brand image and brand awareness from consumer perceptions, it will generate high purchase intention.

CONCLUSION

This research expresses the development of the latest knowledge from previously researched constructs, namely by combining brand trust, brand image and brand awareness, which mediate between social media marketing and purchase intention with Samsung smartphones as the research object. Based on the results of data analysis in this study, the eight hypotheses in this study are accepted, and all hypotheses have a significant positive influence. In the direct effect

test, social media marketing on brand trust has the highest significant positive influence among the results of other direct effect tests. Then, in the indirect effect test, social media marketing on purchase intention through brand awareness as mediation has the highest significant positive influence.

If we look at the problems raised in this research, the Samsung Company in Indonesia can focus on marketing its products through the social media Facebook. With a very large follower on Facebook, the Samsung Company can easily reach its potential consumers. Social media marketing by the Samsung company must combine brand trust, brand image and brand awareness as targets in marketing so that consumers have a high purchase intention for their smartphone products. If the social media marketing carried out by the company can increase brand trust, brand image and brand awareness from consumer perception, then the company will be able to improve the decline in market share that has occurred previously.

Then, based on the R-square test, it is known that although this research produces variables that significantly positively influence purchase intention, some factors or variables are not within the scope of this research. These factors or variables have yet to be considered in this research. Suggestions for research that wants to take on topics similar to this research should consider adding variables that are not within the scope of this research. This aims to ensure that further research obtains more concrete results. Moreover, future research needs to thoroughly examine all research parameters to ensure their suitability to the research objectives in the hope of increasing the relevance and precision of research in the future.

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